

NUMERACY IN ONLINE ASSISTED INSTRUCTIONAL INTERVENTIONS AND THE PROBLEM SOLVING SKILLS OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The use of Online Assisted Instruction during these times of New Normal became a major trend in the field of education in the Philippines. Although there are several researches that discussed its importance, it is still a topic of consideration when it comes to its effect in the learners' numeracy and Problem Solving skills in mathematics. The study aims to determine the relationship between the learners' perception on Online Assisted Instructional Intervention, their numeracy level, and Problem Solving skills. Purposive sampling technique were used to determine the 80 Grade 7 participants from Bitin Integrated National High School (BINHS). Data were gathered in a digitalized method which was administered in various online platforms which utilized a descriptive correlational study. Three separate tests were conducted to measure the participants' perception on Online Learning, Numeracy level, and Problem Solving Skills. The results collected were computed through frequency distribution, mean, percent count and Pearson Moment of Correlation Coefficient. The findings shown that the participants have developing level of numeracy in mathematics. The study concluded that there is a significant relationship between the learners' numeracy level and problem solving skills in terms of identification, elaboration, planning, and executing. Outcomes also revealed that there is no significant relationship and interaction between the participants' perception on Online Assisted interventions and their problem solving skills. It is recommended for future researchers to go beyond the perceptions of students and use other learning variables to yield better results.

Keywords: Online Assisted Instructional Intervention, Numeracy, Problem Solving